

Pointer Analysis for Database-Backed Applications (Supplementary Material)

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A Micro-benchmark: DB-Micro

The interaction between Java applications and databases is inherently complex, involving API calls from database frameworks with diverse and intricate access specifications, as well as SQL with its complex combinations of constructs and underlying semantics. To our knowledge, no benchmark currently exists that systematically captures the key behaviors of these components, posing a challenge for evaluating static analysis tools effectively. To address this, we developed DB-Micro, a suite of micro-benchmarks designed to comprehensively evaluate the capability of static analysis tools in constructing Java-database value flows.

A.1 Overview of DB-Micro

As listed in Table A.1, DB-Micro includes a SQL benchmark and three additional benchmarks for JDBC, JPA, and Spring Data JPA, covering a broad range of database access specifications, as described in Section 1. In total, DB-Micro comprises 824 carefully crafted test cases, designed based on specifications, documentation, and detailed inspections of high-quality real applications, targeting key SQL features and database access APIs essential for constructing value flows in static analysis. Each benchmark provides test cases, ground truth (i.e., value flows generated at runtime by these test cases), and automated evaluation scripts. By converting the output of a static analysis tool into the required JSON format, the scripts can automatically generate an evaluation report.

The first column of each benchmark table in Table A.1 lists the categories of test cases covered by each benchmark. Below, we summarize the four benchmarks (JDBC, JPA, Spring Data JPA and SQL) of Table A.1, and provide two examples to illustrate the details of specific test cases in Section A.2.

JDBC Benchmark. The *Statement* interface is the primary interface for constructing value flows between Java applications and databases. JDBC provides three implementations of this interface: *JdbcPreparedStatement*, *JdbcStatement*, and *JdbcCallableStatement*, each serving different use cases. Based on our study of real-world database-backed applications, the first two are the most commonly used. Therefore, our test cases focus on these implementations, evaluating various APIs for creating and executing statements, and processing their results, resulting in 18 test cases for JDBC.

JPA Benchmark. JPA offers six types of database access APIs, including entity-related APIs (such as *persist* and *find*, with others like *getReference* being similar to *find* and therefore omitted), *Native Query*, *JPQL Query*, *Named Query*, *Criteria Query*, and *StoredProcedure Query*. As *StoredProcedure Query* is rarely used, it was excluded from our tests. Given JPA’s powerful ORM features, the execution of JPA API is influenced not only by the API type but also by factors such as relationships,

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Table A.1. Overview of DB-Micro and the evaluation results of DBridge on DB-Micro.

SQL Benchmark	Test Case	Pass	JDBC Benchmark	Test Case	Pass
insert_constant_value	4	4	manipulate_insert_PreparedStatement	6	6
insert_column_value	1	1	manipulate_update_PreparedStatement	2	2
insert_function_value	2	0	manipulate_select_PreparedStatement	4	4
insert_unary_value	2	2	manipulate_insert_Statement	3	3
insert_nested_value	1	1	manipulate_update_Statement	1	1
insert_math_value	4	4	manipulate_select_Statement	2	2
insert_compare_value	4	4	Sum.	18	18
insert_empty_value	1	1	JPA Benchmark (each row corresponds to one query type, tested under different relationships, entity states, and mappings)	Test Case	Pass
insert_multiple_values	3	3	Persist	54	54
insert_disorder_columns	1	1	Find	54	54
insert_partial_columns	2	2	Native Query	54	54
insert_subquery	1	1	JPQL Query	54	54
update_constant_value	4	4	Named Query	54	54
update_column_value	1	1	Criteria Query	54	0
update_function_value	2	0	Sum.	324	270
update_unary_value	2	2	Spring Data JPA Benchmark (each row corresponds to a query type, tested under different relationships, entity states, and mappings.)	Test Case	Pass
update_nested_value	1	1	Save	54	54
update_math_value	4	4	SaveAll	54	54
update_compare_value	4	4	FindById	54	54
update_multiple_values	3	3	FindAll	54	54
update_where_logical	3	3	Criteria Query	54	26
update_where_in	1	1	Method-Name Query	54	54
update_where_like	2	0	Method-Annotation Query	61	54
update_where_join	4	4	Sum.	385	350
update_alias	2	2	Method-Annotation Query test case	Test Case	Pass
select_constant_value	4	4	annotation_ManyToMany_owning_eager_transient	2	2
select_column_value	3	3	annotation_ManyToMany_owning_eager_persistent	2	2
select_function_value	2	0	annotation_ManyToMany_owning_lazy_transient	2	2
select_unary_value	2	2	annotation_ManyToMany_owning_lazy_persistent	2	2
select_nested_value	1	1	annotation_ManyToMany_inverse_eager_transient	2	2
select_math_value	4	4	annotation_ManyToMany_inverse_eager_persistent	2	2
select_compare_value	4	4	annotation_ManyToMany_inverse_lazy_transient	2	2
select_where_logical	3	3	annotation_ManyToMany_inverse_lazy_persistent	2	2
select_where_in	1	1	annotation_OneToOne_*	16	16
select_where_like	2	0	annotation_ManyToOne_*	16	16
select_where_join	5	5	annotation_Embedded	4	4
select_subquery	1	1	annotation_Inheritance	2	2
select_group_by	2	0	annotation_to_interface	7	0
select_having	2	0	Sum.	61	54
select_alias	2	2			
Sum.	97	83			

entity states, and mappings (Section 2). To ensure comprehensive coverage, we conducted extensive tests across various combinations of these factors, resulting in a total of 324 test cases.

Spring Data JPA Benchmark. Similar to JPA, we tested all types of database access APIs provided by Spring Data JPA, including entity-related APIs (such as *Save*, *SaveAll*, *Find*, and *FindAll*), *Criteria Query*, *Method-Name Query*, and *Method-Annotation Query*, resulting in a total of 385 test cases (as with JPA, *StoredProcedure Query* was excluded due to its rare usage). Due to space limitations, we

Fig. A.1. Examples of two test cases from the JPA and SQL benchmarks in DB-Micro.

further enumerate the detailed test cases for *Method-Annotation Query* (marked in blue in Table A.1), which consists of 61 test cases covering various usage scenarios. Such detailed enumeration also applies to other types of database access APIs, though they are not listed in the table.

SQL Benchmark. SQL provides four types of statements: INSERT, UPDATE, SELECT, and DELETE. We designed test cases for the first three, as DELETE statements pose unique challenges for static analysis. In real database-backed applications, database access APIs can be invoked from any web request, meaning their runtime ordering cannot be reliably determined by static analysis. Handling DELETE statements could improve precision but significantly compromises soundness due to the unordered nature of SQL access. Considering the practical constraints of static analysis, we excluded DELETE-related statements. For the remaining three statement types, we conducted extensive testing, covering a wide range of expressions, clauses, and combinations to ensure thorough evaluation of SQL-related value flow scenarios, yielding a total of 97 test cases.

A.2 Benchmark Examples

Fig. A.1 presents two test cases (① and ④) along with their corresponding ground truth (③ and ⑤). The test case marked as ① corresponds to a case from the “Find” category of the JPA Benchmark, while the test case marked as ④ represents a case from the “select_where_join” category of the SQL Benchmark, both in Table A.1. The JPA test case, defined at line 2, involves saving and querying a People object and its associated Address object. During the execution of the persist API (line 19),

JPA generates and executes two insert SQL statements to save the *People* and *Address* objects into the database (see ②). Similarly, during the execution of the *find* API (line 4), JPA creates and executes two select SQL statements to query the *People* and *Address* tables, converting the query results into a *People* object. In this test case, we compare the *People* object (representing the query result) produced by static analysis (via abstraction and approximation) with the *People* object constructed at runtime (line 5). For the static analysis to succeed, it must correctly handle the semantics of the *persist* and *find* APIs, as well as the four SQL statements (②), producing a *People* object consistent with its runtime version. The JSON representation of the *People* object serves as the ground truth (③). If the static analysis generates the same JSON output, the test case is considered successful.

Our test case focuses exclusively on whether the semantics of the database access APIs and SQL statements are correctly approximated by the static analysis. Since constructs such as branches, loops, or virtual calls—which could introduce imprecision—are excluded from the test cases, we rely on exact matching, rather than over-approximation, to determine whether the static analysis successfully passes a test case.

In the SQL test case (line 29), we primarily assess whether a static analyzer can handle a complex SELECT statement. The JSON in ⑤ represents the data retrieved by the SELECT statement in line 33. This statement incorporates various expressions (arithmetic, logical, comparison, etc.), multiple clauses (inner join, right outer join, and where), and even subqueries. Despite its complexity, DBridge successfully passed the test. This success is attributed to DBridge’s accurate modeling of the database structure and the semantics of SQL’s expressions and clauses from a pointer analysis perspective (Section B.3).

Results of DBridge on DB-Micro. The “Pass” and “Test Case” columns in Table A.1 summarize DBridge’s results across the four micro benchmarks. The former shows the total number of test cases in each category, while the latter indicates how many test cases DBridge successfully passed. In total, DBridge passed 721 out of 824 test cases, a promising result considering the complexity of SQL, database frameworks, and the strict evaluation criteria—where a test case is considered successful only if the static analysis result precisely matches the runtime value flows. Currently, DBridge does not fully support certain features due to their inherent complexity. For example, *select_where_like* involves complex regular expressions, *update_function_value* requires handling intricate arithmetic operations, and a single criterion in *Criteria Query* can involve numerous API calls. We plan to extend DBridge’s capabilities to address these limitations in future work.

B Formalism

In this section, we formalize the core F-primitives and SQL primitives. Section B.1 introduces the notations, along with the database framework and database models that are used throughout the formalization. Then, Sections B.2 and B.3 present the pointer analysis rules for F-primitives and SQL primitives, respectively.

B.1 Notations

Notations. Fig. B.2 summarizes the notations used in our formalism, including those related to primitives. DBridge includes various types of F-primitives and SQL primitives, each with a unique structure. The details of primitives will be provided when discussing their corresponding primitive handlers. Each primitive is assigned a unique identifier (\mathbb{I}) and may include variables ($\mathbb{P}\mathbb{V}$), J-SQL expressions (\mathbb{E}), and constant strings (\mathbb{S}). To facilitate the analysis of Java-to-database interactions through pointer analysis, we model database elements as objects and pointers. Specifically, a table object (in $\mathbb{T}\mathbb{O}$) represents a database table, and row objects (in $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{O}$) represent rows within those

	Primitive IDs	$i, j, k \in \mathbb{I}$	Table Objects	$to_{tn}^{cns} \in \mathbb{TO} \subseteq \mathbb{O}$	
	Primitive Variables	$table, stmt, rs \in \mathbb{PV}$	Column Names	$cns \in \mathbb{S}^0 \cup \mathbb{S}^1 \cup \dots$	
	J-SQL Expressions	$exp \in \mathbb{E}$	Table Names	$tn \in \mathbb{S}$	
	Constant Strings	$name, c, sqlOp \in \mathbb{S}$	Row Objects	$ro_i, ro_j \in \mathbb{RO} \subseteq \mathbb{O}$	
Pointers	$\mathbb{P} = \mathbb{V} \cup (\mathbb{O} \times \mathbb{F}) \cup \mathbb{PV}$	Objects	$o_l \in \mathbb{O}$	Points-to Relations	$pt : \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{O})$

Fig. B.2. Notations.

tables. The database model will be explained further below. We use standard notations to represent pointers, objects, and points-to relations for pointer analysis.

Database Model. In our database model, a table object, denoted as to_{tn}^{cns} , represents a database table. The subscript tn indicates the table name, serving as a unique identifier, while the superscript cns is a list of column names for the table.

A database table can contain multiple rows, modeled through points-to relations. Specifically, a table object to_{tn}^{cns} has a field $to_{tn}^{cns}.rows$ that points to the row objects inserted into the table. Each row in a table may include multiple columns, each holding a value. We represent rows as row objects, and for a given row object ro_i , the field $ro_i.col_l$ denotes the column col_l (where col_l is the column name) within the row. The relationship between a column and its value is also represented using points-to relations, where $ro_i.col_l$ points to the value. Thus, row objects and their fields model rows and their columns, while the values in the rows are represented as Java objects and constants.

This database model allows us to use pointer analysis to simulate operations on the database.

Database Framework Model. Most Java database frameworks are built on JDBC, a Java interface that allows applications to execute SQL statements directly on a database. These frameworks provide APIs to manipulate JDBC statements, which is why the database framework analyzer is designed around JDBC. A JDBC statement encapsulates a J-SQL statement in Java, modeled as a JDBC statement object (so_i) in DBridge. Each so_i contains a field $so_i.sql$, which holds the encapsulated J-SQL statement, and a series of fields $so_i.p_1, \dots, so_i.p_n$, which store the resolved parameters for the statement.

B.2 F-primitives

To model how frameworks manipulate JDBC statements, we define a set of F-primitives, as shown in Fig. B.3. These F-primitives are categorized into four types: New Statement, Initialize Statement, Execute Statement, and Process Result.

The notation for an F-primitive is $P_{kind}\langle \dots \rangle$, where P denotes the primitive type (e.g., N for New Statement), $kind$ specifies the operation within P , and $\langle \dots \rangle$ includes the variables and string constants involved. The details of the specific primitives are explained below.

To analyze Java-to-database interactions, DBridge maintains a global mapping that links each Java entity class to a map containing the corresponding Java-to-database information, e.g., the mapping of class names to table names, and field names to column names. We define a helper function, $getMap(o_l)$, to retrieve the map for a type t , where o_l represents the Class object of t .

New Statement. The New Statement creates a JDBC statement object (so_i) and encapsulates a J-SQL statement in it. Rules [NEW-*] in Fig. B.3 describe the three most commonly used approaches for creating JDBC statements, modeled by the primitives N_{entity} , N_{JPQL} , and N_{native} .

The N_{entity} primitive creates a JDBC statement for variable $stmt$ and generates a J-SQL statement to operate on a specific entity class, referenced by variable $type$, with the operation defined by string $sqlOp$ (e.g., "INSERT", "SELECT"). In [NEW-ENTITY], the helper function $genSQLForEntity$ generates the J-SQL statement based on the specified operation $sqlOp$ and the mapping map between a given

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{i : N_{\text{entity}}\langle \text{stmt}, \text{type}, \text{sqlOp} \rangle \quad o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{type})}{\text{map} = \text{getMap}(o_l)} \quad \text{[NEW-ENTITY]} \quad \frac{i : N_{\text{JPQL}}\langle \text{stmt}, \text{jpql} \rangle \quad o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{jpql})}{\text{map} = \text{getMap}(\text{getEntityType}(o_l))} \quad \text{[NEW-JPQL]} \\
\frac{\text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt})}{\text{genSQLForEntity}(\text{sqlOp}, \text{map}) \in \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})} \quad \frac{\text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt})}{\text{genSQLByJPQL}(o_l, \text{map}) \in \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})} \\
\\
\frac{i : N_{\text{native}}\langle \text{stmt}, \text{sql} \rangle \quad o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{sql})}{\text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt}) \quad o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})} \quad \text{[NEW-NATIVE]} \quad \frac{I_{\text{entity}}\langle \text{stmt}, \text{entity} \rangle \quad \text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt})}{o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{entity}) \quad \text{map} = \text{getMap}(\text{type}(o_l))} \\
\frac{\text{fields} = \text{getFields}(o_l, \text{map})}{\forall 1 \leq x \leq n : \text{pt}(\text{fields}[x]) \subseteq \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.p_x)} \quad \text{[INIT-ENTITY]} \\
\\
\frac{I_{\text{variable}}\langle \text{stmt}, \text{index}, v \rangle \quad \text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt})}{o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{index}) \quad o_h \in \text{pt}(v)} \quad \text{[INIT-VAR]} \quad \frac{E\langle \text{stmt}, \text{rs} \rangle \quad \text{so}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{stmt}) \quad o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})}{\text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}} = \text{executeSQL}(o_l, \text{so}_i.p_1, \dots, \text{so}_i.p_n)} \quad \text{[EXECUTE]} \\
\frac{o_h \in \text{pt}(\text{so}_i.p_{\text{int}(o_l)})}{\text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}} \in \text{pt}(\text{rs})} \\
\\
\frac{i : R_{\text{entity}}\langle \text{rs}, \text{type}, \text{entity} \rangle \quad \text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}} \in \text{pt}(\text{rs})}{\text{ro}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}}.\text{rows})} \quad \text{[RES-ENTITY]} \quad \frac{R_{\text{id}}\langle \text{rs}, \text{entity} \rangle \quad \text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}} \in \text{pt}(\text{rs})}{\text{ro}_i \in \text{pt}(\text{to}_{\text{tn}}^{\text{cns}}.\text{rows}) \quad o_h \in \text{pt}(\text{entity})} \quad \text{[RES-ID]} \\
\frac{o_l \in \text{pt}(\text{type}) \quad \text{map} = \text{getMap}(o_l)}{\text{newEntityObj}(\text{ro}_i, \text{map}, i) \in \text{pt}(\text{entity})} \quad \frac{\text{map} = \text{getMap}(\text{type}(o_h))}{\text{setEntityId}(\text{ro}_i, o_h, \text{map})}
\end{array}$$

Fig. B.3. Pointer analysis rules for key F-primitives. Each rule should be read from the upper half of the horizontal bars, which represents the primitive structure (marked in blue) and premises, down to the lower half of the horizontal bars, which outlines the conclusions.

entity type and a database table. *genSQLForEntity* processes various mappings in detail, which are omitted here for brevity. By [NEW-ENTITY], the created JDBC statement so_i is added to $\text{pt}(\text{stmt})$, and the generated J-SQL statement is added to $\text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})$.

[NEW-JPQL] is similar to [NEW-ENTITY], but instead of generating a J-SQL statement from an entity class, DBridge generates it from a JPQL query. The helper function *getEntityType* identifies the entity class referenced by the JPQL query; e.g., for the query `from org.Article ...`, it resolves `org.Article` as the corresponding entity class. The helper function *genSQLByJPQL* is then used to generate the J-SQL statement based on this JPQL query. In contrast, [NEW-NATIVE] directly uses the provided J-SQL statement from *sql*, assigning it to $\text{pt}(\text{so}_i.\text{sql})$ for the created JDBC statement so_i .

In addition to these primary methods, DBridge also supports other approaches for generating J-SQL statements, such as those based on user-defined methods and annotated methods.

Init Statement. The Init Statement resolves the parameters for a JDBC statement object (so_i) and stores them in its fields $\text{so}_i.p_1, \dots, \text{so}_i.p_n$. The rules [INIT-ENTITY] and [INIT-VAR] describe the two most common approaches for parameter initialization, represented by the primitives I_{entity} and I_{variable} .

The I_{entity} primitive initializes a JDBC statement object referenced by variable *stmt* using the fields derived from the entity object referenced by *entity*. In [INIT-ENTITY], we define two helper functions: *type*, which retrieves the entity class of a given object, and *getFields*, which outputs an array representing the fields of the specified object o_l that needs to be persisted, based on the entity-table map. These fields are used to initialize the parameters of the J-SQL statement. Specifically, the objects pointed to by the k -th field in the array are assigned to $\text{pt}(\text{so}_i.p_k)$.

The I_{variable} primitive initializes a JDBC statement object referenced by *stmt*, where *index* denotes the parameter's position to be initialized, and *v* represents the value used for initialization. In [INIT-VAR], we define the helper function *int*, which converts an integer object to its corresponding int value, serving as the index to identify the specific parameter of so_i to be initialized.

Execute Statement. The Execute Statement executes an initialized JDBC statement. It is represented by the primitive *E*, which executes a JDBC statement referenced by *stmt* and assigns

the result to the variable rs . [EXECUTE] describes this process, where the J-SQL statement o_l and the pointers $so_i.p_1, \dots, so_i.p_n$, which hold the parameter values, are passed to the helper function $executeSQL$. The $executeSQL$ function encapsulates the logic of the database analyzer in DBridge, modeling the execution of various J-SQL statements by generating and processing SQL primitives (see Section B.3 for further details). The output from $executeSQL$ is a table object to_{tn}^{cns} , which contains either the query results or an auto-incremented ID generated by the database analyzer. This table object is subsequently added to $pt(rs)$.

Process Result. The Process Result converts the result of the Execute Statement (i.e., table objects) into Java elements, typically a Java entity or an integer (i.e., the ID of a Java entity), as represented by primitives R_{entity} and R_{id} .

The R_{entity} primitive retrieves the table object referenced by variable rs , converts each row of it into an entity object of the type specified by variable $type$, and assigns the result to variable $entity$. [RES-ENTITY] processes this primitive by first retrieving the result table object to_{tn}^{cns} , its rows, and the entity-table map, then performing the conversion. We define a helper function $newEntityObj$ to handle the conversion, which involves creating an entity object, simulating the invocation of its constructor, and initializing its fields using data from the corresponding column of a row object roj_j , as specified by the entity-table map.

The R_{id} primitive retrieves the table object referenced by the variable rs and uses the database-generated ID stored in this object to set the id field of the entity object referenced by $entity$. [RES-ID] processes this primitive by first retrieving the row roj_i from the result table object. It then performs the helper function $setEntityId$, which transfers the database-generated ID value from the id column of the row object to the id field of the entity object o_n . Specifically, DBridge uses the entity-table map to locate the id field in the entity object, which corresponds to the id column in the database table.

B.3 SQL primitives

We focus on the handling rules for the most essential and commonly used SQL primitives, as shown in Fig. B.4.

SQL primitives are denoted as $op\langle\dots\rangle$, where op represents the type of SQL operation (e.g., create, select), and $\langle\dots\rangle$ contains the variables, J-SQL expressions, and string constants in the primitive. These primitives are processed according to the semantics of the corresponding SQL operations and the database model (see Section B.1). Familiarity with SQL is beneficial for understanding these rules.

The *create* primitive represents the creation of a database table. In this primitive, the variable $table$ points to the newly created table object, while the constant strings $name$ and c_1, \dots, c_n represent the table's name and column names, respectively. This primitive is handled by [CREATE]. It generates a table object $to_{name}^{[c_1, \dots, c_n]}$, which is identified by $name$ and containing the columns c_1, \dots, c_n , and adds this table object to the points-to set of $table$.

The *select* primitive represents a select operation that retrieves values from specific columns of $table$, with column names determined by expressions exp_1, \dots, exp_n , and inserts them into columns c_1, \dots, c_n of a temporary result table $table'$. [SELECT] processes this primitive as follows:

- (1) [Create Result Table] It generates a table object $to_{tn'}^{cns'}$ to represent the result table, where the column names cns' are derived from the primitive. The table name tn' is produced by the helper function $newName$, a hash function that generates a unique name based on the primitive ID i .
- (2) [Generate Result Rows] For each row object roj_j in to_{tn}^{cns} , it generates a corresponding result row object roj_k , where k is a unique ID provided by the helper function $newId$, which—like $newName$ —generates a unique ID based on the primitive ID i and row ID j .

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\text{create}(table, name, c_1, \dots, c_n)}{to_{name}^{[c_1, \dots, c_n]} \in pt(table)} \quad \text{[CREATE]} \quad \frac{i : \text{select}(table, exp_1, \dots, exp_n, table', c_1, \dots, c_n)}{to_{tn'}^{cns'} \in pt(table') \quad ro_j \in pt(to_{tn'}^{cns}.rows)} \\
\frac{\quad}{tn' = newName(i) \quad cns' = [c_1, \dots, c_n] \quad k = newId(i, j)} \quad \text{[SELECT]} \\
\frac{\quad}{to_{tn'}^{cns'} \in pt(table') \quad ro_k \in pt(to_{tn'}^{cns}.rows)} \\
\frac{\quad}{\forall 1 \leq x \leq n : pt(ro_j.col_l) \subseteq pt(ro_k.c_x), \text{ where } col_l = eval(exp_x)} \\
\\
\frac{i : \text{insert}(table, c_1, \dots, c_n, exp_1, \dots, exp_n, param_1, \dots, param_m)}{ro_i \in pt(to_{tn}^{cns}.rows) \quad \forall 1 \leq x \leq n : eval(exp_x, param_1, \dots, param_m) \subseteq pt(ro_i.c_x)} \quad \text{[INSERT]} \\
\\
\frac{\text{update}(table, c_1, \dots, c_n, exp_1, \dots, exp_n, param_1, \dots, param_m)}{\forall 1 \leq x \leq n : eval(exp_x, param_1, \dots, param_m) \subseteq pt(ro_i.c_x)} \quad \text{[UPDATE]} \\
\\
\frac{i : \text{where}(table, exp, param_1, \dots, param_n, table')}{tn' = newName(i) \quad match(ro_j, cns, exp, param_1, \dots, param_n)} \quad \text{[WHERE]} \\
\frac{\quad}{to_{tn'}^{cns} \in pt(table') \quad ro_j \in pt(to_{tn}^{cns}.rows)} \\
\\
\frac{i : \text{join}(table_1, table_2, table)}{ro_j \in pt(to_{tn_2}^{cns_2}.rows) \quad tn = newName(i) \quad cns = concat(cns_1, cns_2) \quad k = newId(i', j)} \quad \text{[JOIN]} \\
\frac{\quad}{to_{tn}^{cns} \in pt(table) \quad ro_k \in pt(to_{tn}^{cns}.rows) \quad m = |cns_1| \quad n = |cns_2|} \\
\frac{\quad}{\forall 1 \leq x \leq m : ro_k.col_l \text{ and } ro_{i'}.col_x \text{ are aliased, where } col_l = concat(tn, col_x)} \\
\frac{\quad}{\forall 1 \leq y \leq n : ro_k.col_h \text{ and } ro_j.col_y \text{ are aliased, where } col_h = concat(tn, col_y)}
\end{array}$$

Fig. B.4. Pointer analysis rules for key SQL primitives. Refer to Fig. B.3's caption for rule explanation.

- (3) [Insert Selected Values] For each column reference expression exp_x , it determines the target column name (e.g., col_l) using a helper function $eval$. The selected values, referenced by $ro_j.col_l$, are then inserted into the corresponding column of the result row, e.g., $ro_k.c_x$.

The *insert* primitive represents the insertion of a new row into a database table $table$. The strings c_1, \dots, c_n denote the column names for the inserted data, and the expressions exp_1, \dots, exp_n calculate the values to be written. Additionally, the variables $param_1, \dots, param_n$ represent the SQL parameters (i.e. $so_i.p_1, \dots, so_i.p_1$ in [EXECUTE] of Fig. B.3), used to calculate the expressions. [INSERT] generates a new row object, ro_i , and adds it to the table object. It then evaluates each expression to compute the values that will be assigned to the corresponding columns in the row object. For example, evaluating a parameter expression exp_x yields the objects pointed to by the corresponding SQL parameter, which are then assigned to $ro_i.c_x$.

For the remaining rules in Fig. B.4, we briefly describe the meaning of each primitive along with the helper functions and notations used. The *update* primitive represents an update operation that modifies columns c_1, \dots, c_n for all rows in $table$, with values computed from exp_1, \dots, exp_n and parameters $param_1, \dots, param_m$. This primitive is handled by [UPDATE]. The *where* primitive represents a filtering operation that selects rows from table $table$ based on a condition evaluated from expression exp with parameters $param_1, \dots, param_n$, and adds the matching rows to a temporary result table $table'$. This primitive is handled by [WHERE], where we define a helper function, $match$, which evaluates whether a given row ro_j meets the filtering expression exp . For instance, if the filtering expression exp is "id=1", only the row object whose id column points to 1 will be selected.

The *join* primitive represents a join operation that combines two tables, $table_1$ and $table_2$, into a temporary result table $table$. This primitive is handled by [JOIN], where we define a helper function, $concat$, to concatenate two lists (e.g., $concat(cns_1, cns_2)$) or two names (e.g., $concat(tn, col_x)$). $|cns_1|$ and $|cns_2|$ represent the number of columns in $table_1$ and $table_2$, respectively. Additionally, in the

conclusion of [JOIN], we define two pointers (e.g., $ro_k.col_l$ and $ro_{i'}.col_x$) as aliased, meaning that the analysis ensures they point to the same objects.